

Supplemental Material

Origin, General Definition, and Implications of Cryosuction in Frozen Soil

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1. Calibration of Soil Sorptive Potential Parameters

The soil sorptive potential ψ_{sorp} generally consists of three components for soils with low salinity (Lu and Zhang 2019; Wang and Lu 2025):

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_{\text{sorp}}(x) &= \psi_{\text{vdW}}(x) + \psi_{\text{ele}}(x) + \psi_{\text{hyd}}(x) \\ &= -\frac{\mathcal{A}}{6\pi x^3} + \frac{m_{\text{ele}}}{x^2} + \psi_{\text{hyd}0}e^{-x/\lambda}\end{aligned}\quad (\text{S1})$$

where ψ_{vdW} , ψ_{ele} , and ψ_{hyd} represent the van der Waals, electrical, and hydration components, respectively (-kPa); \mathcal{A} is the Hamaker constant (J); m_{ele} is the strength of electrical interactions (-N); $\psi_{\text{hyd}0}$ is the surface hydration potential adjacent to the particle surface (-J/m³); and λ is the decay length of the hydration potential (m). Eq. (S1) was fitted to experimental data of the unfrozen water film thickness under freezing conditions for montmorillonite and kaolinite reported in Kruse and Darrow (2017). The calibrated parameter values are summarized in Table S1.

Table S1. Calibrated parameters of the soil sorptive potential.

Soil	\mathcal{A} (J)	m_{ele} (-N)	$\psi_{\text{hyd}0}$ (-Pa)	λ (m)
Montmorillonite	3.2×10^{-20}	7.8×10^{-15}	2.1×10^6	5.7×10^{-10}
Kaolinite	2.0×10^{-20}	2.0×10^{-14}	1.0×10^7	1.7×10^{-10}

2. Driving Force at the Air-Water Interface

Assume that a stable unfrozen water-air interface can persist under subzero temperature conditions, as shown in Fig. 11(a). In this environment, the relative humidity (RH) is assumed to be constant. The phase equilibrium condition at the air-water interface within Plane I can be established via the Kelvin equation (Zhang et al., 2022):

$$p_A^w - p^a + \psi_{\text{sorp}}(f_A) = \frac{RT_A}{v^w} \ln(\text{RH}) \quad (\text{S2})$$

Because the water pressure at point A equals the air pressure, Eq. (S2) can be reduced to:

$$\psi_{\text{sorp}}(f_A) = \frac{RT_A}{v^w} \ln(\text{RH}) \quad (\text{S3})$$

Eq. (S3) implies that, under constant RH ($\leq 100\%$), a lower temperature results in a thicker unfrozen water film thickness, which contrasts with the trend derived from the ice-liquid water interface.

Since points A and D share the same temperature along Plane I, they are considered to be under local thermodynamic equilibrium. Consequently, the water potentials at these two points are identical, and Eqs. (6) through (9) also hold for this case. Thus, the pressure difference between points C and D is therefore given by:

$$\Delta p^w = p_C^w - p_D^w = \psi_{\text{sorp}}(f_B) - \psi_{\text{sorp}}(f_A) \quad (\text{S4})$$

Substituting Eq. (S3) into Eq. (S4) yields Eq. (43).

References:

- Kruse, A. M., and M. M. Darrow. 2017. "Adsorbed cation effects on unfrozen water in fine-grained frozen soil measured using pulsed nuclear magnetic resonance." *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 142: 42–54. Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coldregions.2017.07.006>.
- Lu, N., and C. Zhang. 2019. "Soil sorptive potential: Concept, theory, and verification." *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, 145 (4): 04019006. American Society of Civil Engineers.
- Wang, Y., and N. Lu. 2025. "A Closed-Form Equation for Soil Sorptive Potential." *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, 151 (9). American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE). <https://doi.org/10.1061/jggefkg.teng-13398>.
- Zhang, C., L. Gou, S. Hu, and N. Lu. 2022. "A Thermodynamic Formulation of Water Potential in Soil." *Water Resources Research*, 58 (9). John Wiley and Sons Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022WR032369>.